

EYEBLINK MONITORING AS A MEANS OF MEASURING PILOT PHYSIOLOGICAL STATE

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of the study was to determine whether the Pilot Loss of Consciousness (PLOC) monitor, engineered and built by Energy Optics, Inc. of Las Cruces, NM, is an effective means of detecting g-induced loss of consciousness through monitoring a pilot's eyeblink. The PLOC monitor uses an oxygen mask mounted infrared emitter/receiver and a microprocessor to collect and process the light reflected from the eyelid and sclera to determine when a blink occurs. The method used was to instrument centrifuge subjects for EOG and with the PLOC monitor and monitor the output under sustained acceleration levels from 3 to 7 Gz. The PLOC monitor detected better than 90% of subject blinks during the test. There was no statistically significant difference in performance due to acceleration level or eye color, and no artifact from movement or speech. The PLOC monitor performed well under sustained acceleration and shows potential for use in an in-flight pilot physiological state monitoring system.

INTRODUCTION: Recent developments in fighter aircraft have provided the capability for pilots to experience more g forces with faster onset rates (g/sec) and longer duration than ever before. When excessive G forces and/or high onset rates are experienced by a pilot, G-induced loss of consciousness (GLOC) can occur. Current research is aimed at developing an in-flight loss of consciousness monitoring system. One of the attributes considered for use in the system is the presence or absence of the pilot's eyeblink (1). This paper documents tests on an eyeblink sensing unit, the Pilot Loss of Consciousness (PLOC) monitor.

METHODS AND MATERIALS: PILOT LOSS OF CONSCIOUSNESS MONITOR. The PLOC monitor was developed by Electro Optics of Las Cruces, NM under a USAF small business innovation research program. It consists of a test unit, an electronics assembly and a microprocessor. The electronics assembly consists of an emitter, driver, detector/receiver and amplifying circuits located in a protective housing under the oxygen mask (Figure 1). Three fiber optic cables originate from the housing and converge to a single bundle at the top of the mask. The microprocessor is located in a small aluminum box on the end of a cable connected to the electronics assembly. The test unit is housed

in an aluminum box which contains the remaining electronics, the on/off switch, two LEDs, one for blink and one for alarm, a buzzer, a switch that enables the buzzer to be set for either the blink detection or the alarm mode, a reset button, and a female connection for the processor. The monitor is enabled by the completion of a circuit between the mask bayonets and a wire that connects the bayonet attachment points inside the helmet. When the unit is activated, a visible light is emitted from the fiber optic bundle on the top of the mask for approximately five seconds to assist in aiming the device (Figure 1). The reset button activates the visible light if more time is required.

Figure 1. PLOC monitor.

The monitor uses an infrared emitter that sends out pulses of light that are reflected and collected. The blink signal appears as a small, high frequency perturbation amid the low frequency background noise in the collected light. These analog pulses are converted to a DC level equal to the pulse height. This signal is processed for areas higher in frequency or voltage than the background dv/dt (voltage changes with time) levels. A digital output is produced when either a positive or negative dv/dt exceeds a threshold value. The positive and negative slope signals correspond to the closing and opening of the eye during a blink. The duration of the digital signals and the time periods between their occurrences are analyzed by the microprocessor in determining the presence or

absence of a blink (2).

When a blink is detected, the blink LED flashes and a buzz is heard if the audio is in the blink mode. When a preset amount of time elapses without a blink being detected, the alarm is triggered and the alarm LED lights up and the buzzer sounds if the audio is in the alarm mode.

Two PLOC monitors were used in this test. Both came attached to a regular oxygen mask. The alarm activation times were 12 seconds and 18 seconds. Because the units had to be switched from mask to mask depending on the subject's mask size, the enable circuit using the oxygen mask bayonets and the helmet was shorted. The test unit was modified to allow a voltage to be recorded when a blink was detected.

ACCELERATION PROFILES: The acceleration force environments were created by the Dynamic Environment Simulator (DES), man-rated centrifuge located at the Acceleration Effects Branch, Biodynamics and Bioengineering Division, Armstrong Aerospace Medical Research Laboratory, Wright-Patterson AFB, OH. Four different acceleration profiles were generated for this test. Three profiles used a gradual onset of 0.5g/sec to reach plateaus of 3, 4, and 5 Gz for thirty seconds. The fourth profile was a simulated air combat maneuver with plateaus of 3, 7, 4, 3, 5, 4, 7, 3, and 6 Gz (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Simulated Air Combat Maneuver (SACM) Profile.

TEST SUBJECTS: The six test subjects, three with blue eyes and three with brown, were members of the AAMRL Sustained Acceleration Stress Panel. Each wore a flight suit, gloves, boots, anti-G suit, helmet and oxygen mask equipped with the Pilot Loss of Consciousness monitor. They were instrumented with a standard 3 lead EKG and for EOG with a electrode above the left eye and one on each mastoid.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE: The subjects were placed in the cab of the DES in an ACES II

seat with a 30 degree seatback angle. Each wore a PCU-15 harness with a lap belt. A helmet and mask equipped with the PLOC monitor were placed on the subjects, and the monitor was activated and adjusted. The subject was taken to a baseline of 1.3 Gz. Each test consisted of the four acceleration profiles with a 60 second rest between. Brush recordings of EOG, PLOC monitor blink signal, seatback Gz acceleration level and event marker were taken during the test runs. The event marker was initiated at the onset from baseline and terminated after the plateau upon return to baseline. A split screen consisting of a close-up view of the test subject's face and brush recording of the event marker and the PLOC monitor blink signal was videotaped during the runs. The EOG was used to define any erroneous blink signals from the PLOC monitor. The PLOC monitor blink signals were counted and recorded. The videotape was reviewed and the subject's blinks counted and recorded.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS: An ANOVA was performed using percent of blinks detected by the PLOC monitor as the dependent variable, with profile and eye color as fixed factors and subject a random factor.

RESULTS: The results show the PLOC monitor detected accurately more than 90% of the subject's eyeblinks. There were no significant differences in performance as a function of G level ($p = 0.8865$) or to subject's eye color ($p = 0.9120$).

TABLE 1

PERCENTAGE OF BLINKS DETECTED BY PROFILE (N=6)

Profile	% detected by PLOC monitor	standard deviation
3Gz	90.38	± 9.34
4Gz	91.75	± 5.14
5Gz	92.81	± 10.23
SACM	90.28	± 8.27

TABLE 2

PERCENTAGE OF BLINKS DETECTED BY EYE COLOR (N=6)

Subject eye color	% detected by PLOC monitor
blue	90.96
brown	91.66

DISCUSSION: Although the PLOC monitor blink signal correlated well to the test subject's blinks, there is room for improvement. Several possible areas for improvement were identified in this study. First, the visible light used to assist in aiming the device should stay on longer than five seconds. It is difficult to get an accurate alignment in only five seconds. Fifteen to twenty seconds would be more appropriate. Also, the fiber optic cables leading from the electronics assembly should come in different

lengths for different sizes of oxygen masks. Some problems were encountered with the cables being too long or too short for the various sizes of masks. As a result, the clamp which holds the fiber optic bundle had to be modified for use on long masks. Finally, the fixed time for alarm activation should be eliminated. The principal investigator for the development of the PLOC monitor concluded that the firmware in the microprocessor could be improved to incorporate the eyeblink patterns of an individual pilot when the PLOC monitor is worn (2). This would seem to be the best way to handle the alarm timing, to make it an individual characteristic.

Even with improvements in firmware, it may be a very difficult task to set an alarm time. Several subjects exceeded the 12 second time limit without blinking during the 5 G profile and one subject had difficulty with the 18 second time limit on all profiles. Also, a recent study of workload assessment under sustained acceleration showed that one subject completed several 60 second profiles without a single eyeblink (3).

Although the performance of the PLOC monitor might be improved to the point of detecting 99.9% of pilot eyeblinks (2), accurate detection of G-induced loss of consciousness using a single attribute such as blink activity is improbable. Although it is impractical for the PLOC monitor to be a single attribute in detecting GLOC, it would be a useful attribute in a system that uses several physiological as well as aircraft parameters to determine GLOC.

CONCLUSIONS: The PLOC monitor detected better than 90% of subject's eyeblinks during the experimental profiles. There were no significant differences in the unit's performance as a function of the magnitude of the G force or subject eye color. Possible modifications to improve the performance include a longer period of visible light to assist in aiming the device, different lengths of fiber optic cables for different oxygen mask sizes, and development of firmware that could characterize the eyeblink patterns of individual pilots. The PLOC monitor would be a useful tool in a pilot loss of consciousness monitoring system.

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BIOGRAPHY

Patrick O'Brien is a research aero-astro engineer in the Acceleration Effects Branch, Biodynamics and Bioengineering Division of the Armstrong Aerospace Medical Research Laboratory, Wright-Patterson AFB, OH. He received a B.S. Degree in Aerospace Engineering from the University of Arizona in 1985. He has been involved in research in preflight adaptive training, g-induced loss of consciousness detection and aircrew harness testing.